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HAWTHORN PLANT AND ITS MEDICINAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT. *This article describes the cultivation technologies of the hawthorn plant and its medicinal properties. It discusses the acquisition of medicinal raw materials from hawthorn and the effects of its preparations on human health, along with guidelines for its rational use.*

Keywords: *Hawthorn, medicinal plant, tincture, agrotechnics, antioxidant, cholesterol, vitamins B1, B2, PP, C, E*

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's flora contains 577 species of medicinal plants. Among them, about 120 wild and cultivated species are used in scientific research and traditional medicine. Currently, specialized farms and forest enterprises grow about 42 species to supply industrial and pharmaceutical needs. The hawthorn genus includes over 700 species, mainly found in North America. About 50 species are found in the CIS. Due to introduction efforts, a collection of 92 species was established in the Tashkent Botanical Garden.

RESEARCH MATERIALS

HAWTHORN (CRATAEGUS)

GENUS This genus consists of numerous tree and shrub species. Trees reach 10–15 m in height, while shrubs grow 0.5–4 m tall. Trunks are 40–50 cm thick, with dense branching. The genus has about 890 species, 10 of which grow in Uzbekistan, and are also spread across China, Spain, Italy, Algeria, America, etc. Leaves are serrated or lobed, arranged alternately on the

stem, with 22–30 mm petioles, sometimes with glands. Flowers are small and white, gathered in inflorescences. Fruits are 1–5-seeded. They can be single- or multi-stemmed, with thorny short branches and long shoots that are gray or yellow with white lenticels. The fruit is hairy, round to pear-shaped, angular, 2–5 cm in diameter, and comes in red, dark red, yellow, black, and brown. The flesh varies in color and taste. In China, the taste resembles apples. Seeds range from 1–5 and vary in shape. The fruit ripens in autumn and remains on the tree until the first frost.

1. Yellow hawthorn (Crataegus pontica C.Koch.) Fruits are edible, and the plant reproduces by seeds. The fruit is pentagonal, orange-red, and 1.7 cm wide. The root system lies 50–60 cm below the soil and extends 5–10

m from the trunk, being 15 times wider than the crown.

Yellow hawthorn tree and fruit (Crataegus pontica C.Koch.)

2. Turkestan or Red hawthorn (Crataegus turkestanica Pojark.) Native to the Tien Shan, Pamir, Alai, and Kopetdag mountains, it grows naturally on rocky slopes and valleys up to 2000 m above sea level. It reaches 8 meters in height. The fruit ripens in October, is oval, up to 12 mm in diameter, red, shiny, with yellow fuzz, and has one stone. The fruit lesh is inedible.

RESULTS

1. Chemical composition of hawthorn. Hawthorn fruits contain 20 percent fiber, 8 percent fat, flavonoids, choline, acetylcholine, tannins, carotene, vitamin C, organic acids, etc. Some types of hawthorn growing in Uzbekistan have been found to contain vitamins B1, B2, RR, C, E.

2. Useful properties of hawthorn. Hawthorn decoction, alcohol decoction and extract of hawthorn are recommended by doctors to patients with diseases such as angioneurosis (neurosis of blood vessels, functional disease of blood vessels), heart failure, increased blood pressure, **heart failure** in patients with infectious diseases. Everyone knows hawthorn fruits. Since ancient times, infusions from the fruits and flowers of this magical plant have been a universal remedy for all diseases. Not only traditional medicine, but also modern science uses the beneficial properties of the plant for various diagnoses.

Fruits, flowers, and even leaves protect our health. Hawthorn is considered one of the healthiest fruits in the world and is beneficial for the following diseases: It is indispensable in improving **heart function**, it is used in the treatment of heart failure: the fruits eliminate both tachycardia and bradycardia. Restores heart rhythm. Hawthorn is a powerful **antioxidant**. It helps neutralize unstable molecules called free radicals that can harm the body. Due to their antioxidant activity, polyphenols reduce the risk of certain cancers, type 2 diabetes, and asthma. In traditional Chinese medicine, hawthorn is one of the most recommended foods for the treatment of high blood pressure. The plant has a vasodilating effect. It lowers **cholesterol** levels. High cholesterol levels can be the cause of atherosclerosis, and accordingly, cardiovascular diseases can develop. Hawthorn phytopreparations help eliminate or reduce pathologies of the coronary arteries, normalize capillary blood flow disorders, and eliminate the effects of tissue hypoxia. Hawthorn is also useful for the gastrointestinal tract, in particular for the treatment of indigestion. Hawthorn fruit contains fiber that acts as a prebiotic and aids digestion. Hawthorn is beneficial for the nervous system, fights frequent headaches, normalizes sleep and eliminates neurosis, has a calming effect. It has a sedative effect that helps reduce symptoms of unreasonable anxiety. Currently, hawthorn is being studied as a potential tool for treating central nervous system diseases such as anxiety and depression. Herbal preparations with hawthorn are actively used in the treatment of women's health problems. Tea, decoctions, infusions help eliminate tissue hypoxia, reduce the severity of migraines, and normalize the level of sex hormones. It also helps slow down the aging process and preserves youthful skin. Tea with hawthorn eliminates swelling and enhances metabolic processes.

DISCUSSION

1. Be careful when using hawthorn and follow the norm. The amount of fresh hawthorn berries should not exceed one glass per day. It should be remembered that an overdose can threaten a strong decrease in pressure. This is

especially important for people with low blood pressure.

2. In addition to fresh fruits, hawthorn can be consumed in the form of jelly, compote. The dosage is the same - one glass, a maximum of one and a half per day.

3. Doctors absolutely prohibit the use of hawthorn even for expectant mothers. This can lead to the risk of premature birth or bleeding.

4. Among the main prohibitions is the use of decoctions or infusions on an empty stomach - hawthorn irritates the mucous

membrane of the digestive tract and can lead to exacerbation of chronic diseases, provoke intestinal spasms.

CONCLUSION

A homemade syrup can be made from hawthorn fruits by boiling 25 g of fruit in 200 g of hot water until thickened. Take 40 drops after meals three times a day. A decoction can be made from dried flowers: pour a glass of boiling water over two tablespoons of flowers, simmer for 10 minutes, strain, and take one tablespoon three times a day.

REFERENCES USED

1. Qayimov A.Q. Dendrologiya —T; «Ilm-ziyo».2007.

2. Dorivor o'simliklarni yetishtirish texnologiyasi [text] : textbook / O'. Axmedov [and oth.]. - Tashkent : Shafoat Nur Fayz,2020. - 232 p.

3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-251 dated May 20, 2022 "On measures to organize the cultural cultivation and processing of medicinal plants and their widespread use in treatment."

4. X.X. Xolmatov, O'.A. Ahmedov–Farnakognoziya. Tashkent. “Fan” publisher 2007y.

5. E.T. Berdiev, M.X. Xakimova, G.B. Maxmudova. O'rmon dorivor o'simliklari (textbook). - Tashkent, Minitypography of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016. - 252 pages.

6. A.A. Xonazarov O'zbekistonda o'rmonzorlar barpo qilish asoslari T- 2002

7. G. Turayeva, U. Fayzullayev “Do'lana o'simligini yetishtirish va uning dorivorlik xususiyatlari” Challenges of storage and processing of agricultural products and their solutions based on modern technologies” international scientific and practical conference october 22, 2024